

Adverb Placement in Learner Writing: The Effect of Linguistic Features, Cross-Linguistic Transfer and Register

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Due to their syntactic mobility, adverbs lend themselves well to first-language (L1)-related syntactic transfer studies (Hasselgård, 2015); however, there is a limited body of research looking into what other factors may influence clause placement. With the exception of Larsson et al (2020), which investigated the impact of linguistic, extralinguistic and L1 transfer-related factors on adverb placement, most previous studies have focused on overuse-underuse analysis and misuse of adverbs. Moreover, very few studies go beyond the realm of well-studied Germanic and Romance languages. The present study is a partial replication study of Larsson et al.'s (2020) and revisits the question of whether adverb placement can help us detect L1 transfer; it also looks at the possible effect of linguistic (e.g., presence/absence of an auxiliary), extralinguistic variables (e.g., native-speaker status, L1 background) and register. However, the aim is not only to see if those findings can be replicated on German and native-speaking students, but also to extend our knowledge by also looking at Turkish, a language that is very different from English typologically.

The data were obtained from two different corpora; the International Corpus of Learner English (ICLE) and the Louvain Corpus of Native English Essays (LOCNESS). The study looks at the following 15 epistemic adverbs (Granath, 2005): maybe, probably, possibly, really, simply, actually, apparently, certainly, clearly, definitely, evidently, obviously, perhaps, surely, and of course.

The results show that German learners behaved more native-like than their Turkish counterparts who overused the clause initial (e.g., Probably she is here) and underused the clause-medial position. Similar to Larsson et al.'s (2020) findings, the main predictors of adverb placement are linguistic rather than extralinguistic; although some traces of L1 transfer were found with Turkish data. Moderate effect of register on variation in learner writing was also reported.